

Open-end Winding Induction Machine Supplied by Two Flying Capacitor Multilevel Inverters

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Abstract—In this paper the authors propose the open-end winding induction machine supplied by two multilevel inverters with flying-capacitor, two PWM strategies, phase-shifting PWM and phase-disposition-band are presented. A generalized mathematical model of the « n » levels inverters feeding the open-end stator winding induction machine is presented. An extended generalized multilevel PWM strategy is carried out to control the inverter.

Keywords—Open-end winding induction machine; Multilevel inverter;

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of PEBB (Power Electronic Building Block) initiated by the ONR (Office of Naval Research) and CPES (USCenter of Power Electronics System), aims to improve reliability, modularity, standardization, scalability, reconfigurability and reducing the cost of electrical systems in many fields such as railways applications, aeronautics, electrical propulsion of ships and electrical vehicles systems...

The power segmentation of electrical machines and converters is now a major interest in electrical engineering researches. An considerable interests are given for multiphase machines, where each phase is supplied by its own voltage inverter [1]-[2], multi star asynchronous machines, where each star is supplied by its own three phase voltage inverter [3]-[4]-[5] and open-end stator windings machines [6]-[7]-[8]-[9]. Several researches have also been developed in converter structures including multilevel inverters with flying-capacitor, two-level cascaded inverters, H-Bridge inverters ... [10]-[11]-[12]- [13]-[14].

The authors devote this paper to the supply of the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine by multilevel structures with flying-capacitor. Two types PWM strategies are used:

- Phase-shifting PWM
- Phase disposition PWM

A THD analysis is presented for the two types PWM strategies.

Finally this article gives the mathematical model for the supply of the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine by two «n» levels inverters.

II. MODEL OF SIMULATION FOR VOLTAGE SUPPLY

If the open-end winding asynchronous machine is supplied by two sources of voltage. The mathematical flux model is written in (d,q) reference frame, and described by the following state equation representation:

$$\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = [A(\omega, \omega_{dq})][X(t)] + [B] U(t) \quad (1)$$

$$Y(t) = [C] . X(t)$$

With:

$$X(t) = [\Phi_{sd} \quad \Phi_{sq} \quad \Phi_{rd} \quad \Phi_{rq}]^T : \text{State vector}$$

$$U(t) = U_1(t) - U_2(t) = [V_{sd1} \quad -V_{sd2} \quad V_{sq1} \quad -V_{sq2}]^T : \text{Control vector}$$

$$Y(t) = [I_{sd} \quad I_{sq} \quad I_{rd} \quad I_{rq}]^T : \text{The output vector}$$

The functional diagram is given by figure 1:

Figure 1. Functional diagram of the open-end winding machine.

From the equation (1):

$$[I] = [L]^{-1} . [\Phi] \quad (2)$$

With

$$T_s = \frac{L_s}{R_s} \quad \text{Constant of time for the stator.}$$

$$T_r = \frac{L_r}{R_r} \quad \text{Constant of time for the rotor.}$$

$$\sigma = 1 - \frac{M_{sr}^2}{L_s L_r} : \text{Coefficient of dispersion of Blondel.}$$

The matrix [A]

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sigma T_s} & \omega_{dq} & \frac{M_{sr}}{\sigma T_s L_r} & 0 \\ -\omega_{dq} & \frac{1}{\sigma T_s} & 0 & \frac{M_{sr}}{\sigma T_s L_r} \\ \frac{M_{sr}}{\sigma T_r L_s} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma T_r} & \omega_{dq} - \omega \\ 0 & \frac{M_{sr}}{\sigma T_r L_s} & -(\omega_{dq} - \omega) & \frac{1}{\sigma T_r} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The matrix [B]

$$[B] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The matrix [C]

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} & 0 & \frac{-M_{sr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} & 0 & \frac{-M_{sr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} \\ \frac{-M_{sr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-M_{sr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The drive mechanical equation is given as follows:

$$T_{em} - T_r = j \frac{d\omega}{dt} + f \omega \quad (6)$$

$$T_{em} = \frac{3}{2} p (\Phi_{s\alpha} I_{s\beta} - \Phi_{s\beta} I_{s\alpha}) \quad (7)$$

T_{em} : Electromagnetic torque

T_r : Load torque

A. Validation of the model of the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine

The model of simulation is validated in the environment of « Matlab simlink ».

In figure 2, the open-end winding induction machine is fed by two PWM voltage source inverters based on V/f law.

Figure 2. Open-end winding IM supplied by two 2 levels inverters PWM.

B. Control signals

To supply the open-end winding induction machine by two voltage source inverters, we used a carrier PWM.

Figure 3 shows the reference voltage V_{ref11} and V_{ref21} with the triangular signal for the control of the two two-level inverters.

Figure 3. Signal of V_{ref11} and V_{ref21} with a triangular signal for the control of inverter 1 and 2

C. The phase voltage of the machine

Figure 4 shows the phase voltage (V_{s11} - V_{s21}) and the pole voltage machine $U_1 = (V_{s11}-V_{s12}) - (V_{s21}-V_{s22})$.

With

V_{s11} , V_{s12} simple voltage of inverter 1

V_{s11} - V_{s12} pole voltage of inverter 1

V_{s21} , V_{s22} simple voltage of inverter 2

V_{s21} - V_{s22} pole voltage of inverter 2

Figure 4. Phase-to-phase inverter voltage and phase-to-phase machine voltage.

Figure 5 shows the waveform of the phase-to-phase machine voltage and the harmonic content of the voltage.

Figure 5. Waveform and harmonic ration of machine voltage.

III. OPEN-END STATOR WINDING ASYNCHRONOUS MACHINE FED BY MULTILEVEL INVERTER

A flying-capacitor « n » levels inverter consists of three arms; each arm contains « p » cells. The structure of supply of the open-end stator winding induction machine by two inverters is shown figure 6.

Figure 6. Feeding open-end stator winding machine by flying-capacitors multilevel inverter

A. Feeding open-end stator winding asynchronous machine with phase-shifting PWM

1) *Principle of the phase-shifting PWM strategy:* In the phase-shifting PWM strategy, the references signals of frequency f_m and amplitude A_m are compared with the triangular carrier of frequency f_p and A_p amplitude, shifted between them of an angle $(\frac{2\pi}{n-1})$. Figure 7 represents the phase-shifting PWM strategy for inverter by « p » cells.

Figure 7. Principle of the phase-shifting PWM for inverter by « p » cells.

2) *Feeding by four level inverters:* the multilevel structure with open-end stator winding induction machine is shown in figure 8. The machine is fed by two four-level inverters.

Figure 8. Feeding open-end stator winding machine by four level inverter

Three triangular carriers are used to generate switching signals of each arm of the four-level inverter. Figure 9 shows three triangular signals and a reference signal.

Figure 9. Signal reference with three triangular carriers.

The figure 10 shows pole voltage with inverter 1 ($V_{s11} - V_{s12}$) and inverter 2 ($V_{s21} - V_{s22}$) and phase-to-phase machine voltage $U_1 = (V_{s11} - V_{s12}) - (V_{s21} - V_{s22})$. Indeed from supply by four levels inverter, we obtain 7 levels of phase-to-phase machine voltage.

Figure 10. Evolution of the Phase-to-phase inverter voltage and phase-to-phase machine voltage.

Figure 11 shows the waveform of the phase-to-phase machine voltage and the harmonic content of the voltage.

Figure 11. Waveform and harmonic ration of machine voltage.

Figure 12 shows the pole voltage machine U_1 , the currents stator I_{sa} , I_{sb} , speed and the torque, for load torque $T_r = T_n$.

Figure 12. Evolution of voltage, currents of stator, speed, and torque.

B. Feeding open-end stator winding asynchronous machine with phase disposition PWM strategy.

1) *Principle of the phase disposition PWM strategy:* In the phase disposition PWM, the reference signals modulating of frequency f_m and amplitude A_m are compared with $(n-1)$ triangular carriers, with the same frequency f_p and amplitude

$$A_{pp} = \frac{A_p}{n-1}$$

Figure 13. Principle of the phase disposition PWM strategy for inverter by « p » cells

2) *Feeding by four levels inverter:* Figure 14 shows three triangular carriers and a signal reference.

Figure 14. Signal reference with three triangular carriers.

Figure 15 shows the voltage $(V_{s11} - V_{s12})$, $(V_{s21} - V_{s22})$ and phase-to-phase machine voltage U_1 which is 7 levels to supply with two four-level inverters of voltage.

Figure 15. Evolution of the Phase-to-phase inverter voltage and phase-to-phase machine voltage.

Figure 16 shows the waveform of the phase-to-phase machine voltage and the harmonic content of the voltage.

Figure 16. Waveform and harmonic ration of machine voltage.

IV. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF « N » LEVELS INVERTER FOR FEEDING OPEN-END STATOR WINDING INDUCTION MACHINE

The flying-capacitor multilevel inverter structure represented in figure 17, consists of three arms, each arm contains « p » cells, and requires « n-1 » capacitors.

Figure 17. Structure of the inverter with flying-capacitor

Notations:

n : fictitious neutral.

i : index indicating the number of the phase i , $i = \{1,2,3\}$

j : index indicating the number of the cell j , $j = [1 \dots p]$

$T(i,j)$, $T'(i,j)$: power switches.

$S(i,j)$: the corresponding switching signal of the $T(i,j)$

$S' i,j$: the corresponding switching signal of the $T'(i,j)$.

The $S(i,j)$ and $S'(i,j)$ are complementary signals.

The three voltages are obtained directly by the following expressions:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{An} \\ V_{Bn} \\ V_{Cn} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{3p} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^p S(1,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S(2,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S(3,j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The voltages between two phases are connected to the simple voltage by the following expressions:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{AB} \\ V_{BC} \\ V_{CA} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{AO} \\ V_{BO} \\ V_{CO} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

To supply the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine, we need two flying-capacitor inverters by « n » levels.

To model the operation of the two inverters, we can deduce from the previous study the following results assuming that the DC bus of each converter is equal to E :

For inverter 1, the simple voltages are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1n} \\ V_{B_1n} \\ V_{C_1n} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{3p} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(1,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(2,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(3,j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The voltages between two phases of inverter 1 are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1B_1} \\ V_{B_1C_1} \\ V_{C_1A_1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1O} \\ V_{B_1O} \\ V_{C_1O} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

For inverter 2, the simple voltages are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_2n} \\ V_{B_2n} \\ V_{C_2n} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{3p} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(1,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(2,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(3,j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The voltages between two phases of inverter 2 are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_2B_2} \\ V_{B_2C_2} \\ V_{C_2A_2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{A_2O} \\ V_{B_2O} \\ V_{C_2O} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The modelling of the operation of the two inverters:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1A_2} \\ V_{B_1B_2} \\ V_{C_1C_2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{3p} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(1,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(1,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(2,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(2,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(3,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(3,j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

The voltages between two phases of this machine:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1B_1} - V_{A_2B_2} \\ V_{B_1C_1} - V_{B_2C_2} \\ V_{C_1A_1} - V_{C_2A_2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1A_2} \\ V_{B_1B_2} \\ V_{C_1C_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

That is to say:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{A_1B_1} - V_{A_2B_2} \\ V_{B_1C_1} - V_{B_2C_2} \\ V_{C_1A_1} - V_{C_2A_2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{p} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(1,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(1,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(2,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(2,j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^p S_1(3,j) - \sum_{j=1}^p S_2(3,j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Figure 18 shows the validation of the mathematical model correspond to the equations (11), (13) for 4 levels.

Figure 18. Evolution of the Phase-to-phase inverter voltage and phase-to-phase machine voltage obtained by mathematical model.

The characteristics of the machine used:

- Nominal power $P = 45$ KW.
- Speed $n = 1450$ rpm.
- Resistance of stator $R_s = 0.15 \Omega$.
- Resistance of rotor $R_r = 0.046 \Omega$.
- Inductance of stator $L_s = 17.9$ mH.
- Inductance of rotor $L_r = 18.6$ mH.
- Mutual inductance $M_{sr} = 17.2$ mH.

V. CONCLUSION

We implemented the simulation model of the open-end winding asynchronous machine supplied by two voltage sources multilevel inverters in the environment of « Matlab Simulink ».

We used two types of control strategies, phase-shifting PWM and phase disposition PWM. An extended generalized multilevel PWM strategy is carried out.

The results of simulation show that the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine has the advantage of increasing the level of phase-to-phase machine voltage. Indeed if we supply the machine by two « n » levels inverters, the level of phase to phase machine voltage is equal to $N = 2n-1$.

The supply of the open-end stator winding asynchronous machine by multilevel inverters clearly improves the THD voltage and extends the band-width particularly with the phase-shifting PWM strategy.

We developed a mathematical model generalized for the supply with two flying capacitors multilevel inverters of this open-end stator winding machine. This model was validated in the « Matlab Simulink » environment, it reduced the simulation time and simplified the schemes realised with Power System Blocks.

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